

Reconsidering the ‘Public’ / ‘Private’ Divide to Realise Societal Welfare in Data Access and Governance

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Abstract

Infraethical theoretical accounts have exposed the limitations in seeing the individual decisions of data owners as a proxy for whether particular types of data access serve the ‘public good’. These limitations are all the more apparent in the post-C19 world, where public health objectives heavily rely on massive, timely and adequate data flows. Drawing on the UK and EU data protection legal frameworks, this paper interrogates the conventional, often rigidly observed, divide between the ‘public’ and ‘private’ interests as bases for lawful data processing. In doing so, it argues against treating the relationship between the two as a zero-sum game. A conceptualisation of the ‘public’ interest as not incompatible with private interests, as long as a contribution to societal well-being is made through data access, is offered in that regard.

Keywords – data sharing; data access; data governance; public benefit; private interests

1 Introduction

The ongoing crisis generated by the coronavirus pandemic, among its many significant repercussions, has made apparent that the ‘public interest’ in collecting and processing data may be dissociable from the organisational interests of particular public-sector data owners. From the early days of the pandemic, public bodies (e.g. hospitals, law enforcement authorities and border control authorities) have had to collaborate closely with private actors (e.g. private sector employers, telecommunications companies and the transport industry) with a view to effectively monitoring the spread of the disease and enforcing appropriate measures to achieve its containment.

Yet, such EU data protection authorities as the CNIL in France and the Garante in Italy have confined the

legitimate undertaking of data processing activities in the name of ‘public health’ to ‘public’, as opposed to ‘private’, actors. For example, both authorities have advised private sector employers against actively collecting data about their employees’ health status (Mole et al, 2020), at the same time that a similar measure would be legitimately employed by migration officers in an airport. Differential treatment of this kind reflects a broader understanding of ‘public’ and ‘private’ interests under lawful grounds for data processing as a zero-sum game. The ‘public interest’ is construed as the realm of public authorities, which are often advised against relying on other grounds for processing, associated with private interests, such as ‘legitimate interests’ (ICO, 2018).

This paper seeks to challenge this competitive, zero-sum understanding of the relationship between the ‘public interest’ and ‘private interests’, arguing that it unduly confines the ‘public’ interest to the organisational priorities of public-sector data owners. The argument is made, instead, that the ‘public’ interest shall be construed by reference to the contribution of a data processing activity to social welfare, shifting attention to the risks and benefits for data subjects, as well as the required governance safeguards for legitimate data processing. The analysis proceeds in three steps.

First, the paper draws on (1) infraethics to demonstrate the limitations in seeing the individual decisions of data owners as a proxy for whether particular types of data access serve the ‘public good’, particularly in the post-C19 world. Second, it provides an (2) analysis of the conventional understanding of the ‘public’/‘private’ divide in UK and EU data protection law and reflects on its limitations in the practice of data governance. Third, it makes the case for (3) overcoming this divide, suggesting

that a data owner's organisational identity shall not be relied upon as a proxy for serving the 'public interest'. It is the contribution of a proposed access request to social well-being that should play a more central role in this assessment. The paper (4) concludes by highlighting key requirements for realising appropriate legal and ethical models of data governance, in the interest of combating power asymmetries and consolidating trust in public-sector data management and security.

2. The Trouble with Strictly 'Controlled' Access: Infraethics and C-19

Data access in the UK public sector is, by and large, governed in a *controlled* or *restricted* way (Dyke et al, 2018). Researchers and other interested parties, as long as they satisfy certain requirements, apply for access on an ad-hoc, *case-by-case* basis. Their applications, often accompanied by comprehensive research proposals, are reviewed and approved by the data owners themselves (Ramos et al, 2012). By contrast, *registered* access models envisage the provision of access to users by reference to their *credentials* (eg researchers affiliated with recognised institutions or complying with specific accreditation requirements) and *risk analysis*, rather than requiring a case-by-case decision on a specifically described project. The EDRU model, standing for 'evidence-based', 'default-open', 'risk-managed' and 'user-centred', is such an example of a registered access approach (Ritchie 2014; Ritchie 2016; Green and Ritchie 2016).

Quite often, the controlled access model creates power dynamics which are not difficult to imagine between the data owner and the requesting party. The content and purpose of the proposed research matters, with its alignment with the data custodian's policy objectives regularly playing a decisive role in the outcome. In that sense, the organisational priorities of a particular public body operate as a proxy for the 'public interest' in facilitating access to administrative data for research purposes. This model, then, confines decision-making authority for data governance and access to individual organisations and appeals to their organisational rationality as a safeguard for appropriate data sharing and (re)use.

In the advent of increasing datafication and employment of algorithmic techniques in the public sector, ethicists have

challenged the soundness of seeing individual decisions as the focal element of governance systems. More specifically, infraethics (or infrastructure ethics) have fleshed out the increasing significance of collective and societal aspects of modern life. As new information and communication technologies add complexity to interpersonal and organisational interactions, infraethics shift attention from individual morality and agency towards non-individual decision-making and accountability (Hess et al, 2018). The interlinked character of such technical innovations as big data techniques and their use in public policy-making bring to the fore the relational nature of such central moral notions as power and responsibility in the context of data access (Zwitter, 2014). Notions of societal and collective well-being are needed to capture this shift, by contrast to individualised interests and entitlements.

The coronavirus pandemic has made the problems with seeing data providers' individual interests as central in data access all the more apparent. With public health objectives increasingly relying on massive, timely and adequate data flows, the handling of C-19 by the UK government demonstrates the lack of transparency and accountability in public data management. A recent data sharing agreement between Amazon and the National Health Service (NHS) allowed the multinational free access to patients' data in exchange for provision of personalised medical advice through its Alexa product. Critical scrutiny of the data sharing agreement brought to the fore the asymmetries of power between the two organisations, as well as the lack of transparency as to the particular rights and duties that Amazon would have over patients' data (Privacy International, 2019).

Where does the authority of public-sector data owners to act as the sole arbiters of the 'public interest' come from? While there are certainly numerous factors at play, e.g. the organisational history of public bodies which are entrusted with managing sensitive datasets or policy aspirations to

maximise the impact of using administrative data, the legal framework is an important source of authority.

3. The ‘Public’ - ‘Private’ Divide in Data Protection Law and its Limitations

UK and EU data protection law establishes the authority of public-sector bodies to process data in the public interest. Article 6(1)(e) GDPR, which is transposed into UK law via section 8 of the Data Protection Act 2018, provides that processing is lawful as long as it is ‘necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest’. How clear-cut is, however, the distinction between the ‘public’ interest and non-public interests? Should we rely on the interpretation of data providers as to this crucial distinction?

The practice of data access and governance indicates that there are significant challenges around implementing a satisfactory definition of the ‘public interest’ as a criterion for classifying the users of a data infrastructure. In some cases, the independent character of research, e.g. academic research, is used as a proxy for research in the public interest. Are all types of independent research, though, legitimate and acceptable? In classifying different categories of data users, many existing initiatives distinguish between academic and commercial researchers (Price, 2015). For example, data-intensive research investments such as the UK Economic and Social Research Council-funded Administrative Data Research Network (ADRN) used this delineation to confine its data sharing to academic researchers. The ADRN justified this approach, in part, by reference to public attitudes (IPSOS Mori, 2016).

Even when commercial access to data is not precluded, many existing data infrastructures still utilise this distinction to impose different requirements upon academic researchers and commercial organisations. One example is the UK Data Service and its Secure Lab, which employs different pathways in granting access to its data based on whether the user is a UK academic researcher, a local government authority, a charity, a non-UK user or a commercial organisation. The HMRC Data Access Panel

also predominantly confines access to its data to non-commercial entities (Welpton and Wright, 2012). Originally, the HMRC panel accepted applications only from researchers based at a UK academic institution or government department. In April 2018, however, it opened up access to its data to commercial research groups, although such data sharing is restricted to projects commissioned by a government department.

Whilst organisational identity is a well-understood and widely-used criterion, it also suffers from a number of weaknesses, particularly when considered in light of modern data processing activities. As a criterion, it is insufficiently nuanced to reflect the intricacies of multi-stakeholder data sharing for research. A series of recent data governance controversies demonstrate that the organisational identity of a user is insufficient alone to justify different treatment towards the sharing of data (Lewis et al, 2018). Moreover, a rigid delineation of users based on organisational identity might pre-empt the potential of certain types of organisations to contribute to the production of high-quality research that may be used to improve public service delivery.

With these concerns in mind, one alternative to organisational identity is to classify users based on their intended use of data, i.e. their purpose behind accessing the infrastructure’s resources and performing data analysis on them. The UK Data Service has followed this approach in articulating different requirements for the users of its Secure Lab distinguishing between *commercial* and *non-commercial use*: The former corresponds to research where the ‘*direct objective* is to generate revenue and/or where data are requested for sale, resale, loan, transfer or hire’ (emphasis added). The latter refers to data uses that seek to support ‘a public good (...) i.e. an activity which widens access to information sourced from our collection and has social or economic benefit’ as a result of the use.

While data use is a more dynamic and context-specific definitional approach, there is still the risk of ambiguity when trying to pin down the meaning of subjective concepts like the ‘intended use of data’. Using the UK Data Service example, it is not entirely clear how a ‘direct’ objective to generate revenues may be distinguished from a relevant ‘indirect’ objective. There are certain organisational requirements and limitations associated with

the outcomes of interpreting such an objective and they can be onerous for potential users.

Considering these limitations in clearly demarcating ‘public’ from ‘non-public’ interests, it is apparent that data providers shall be expected to exercise a certain amount of discretion, often resulting in their decisions with regard to data access suffering from lack of consistency and transparency. To overcome this unsatisfactory state of affairs, the next section proposes an alternative principled way of designing data access and governance.

4. Challenging the Divide: Societal Welfare as a Proxy for the ‘Public Good’

To dissociate the ‘public’ interest from the individual interests of data providers, I propose a classification that is structured around the notion of *societal* or *collective* welfare, as reflected e.g. in such broader political goals as the standard of living, productivity or other metrics of collective well-being. Potential research users of administrative data would be categorised as following:

- A. *Public interest research* – when the research project exclusively serves political aims that pursue the collective or societal welfare
- B. *Proprietary research* – when the research project exclusively serves private interests of a proprietary nature
- C. *Hybrid research* – when the research project serves *both* the collective welfare and private interests of a proprietary nature

This classification would require considering a proposed project’s substantive relevance to the public interest, as reflected in collective, societal values that are worth pursuing. This would shift attention from individual data providers, as well as from the organisational identity of data users as commercial or non-commercial entities. Emphasis would be laid, instead, on the potential of a proposed data use to contribute to the realisation of major societal aims. Subject to an approving risk analysis, data providers would be in principle required to provide access

to data, as long as the requesters are able to demonstrate that such a contribution will take place.

Is the proposed classification consistent with the data protection principles? By law, public-sector data providers are currently allowed to grant access to their data for research purposes *only* when such research is ‘in the public interest’ [ss. 64, 71(4) Digital Economy Act 2017]. This clearly includes Type A research, commonly associated with academics, but not Type B research, commonly associated with corporate entities. However, the notion of ‘public interest’ has not yet been authoritatively interpreted by the Courts and thus there is some ambiguity in the treatment of Type C research. These challenges are inherent in the interpretation and reconciliation of normative categories that are not necessarily mutually exclusive, yet often create conflicts in practice (Laurie et al, 2018).

With the notion of ‘public interest’ being notoriously elusive, invoking collective welfare by itself will not suffice for the establishment of a both robust and facilitative data access model. Especially with regard to ‘hybrid’ cases, where private entities request access to data by promising to produce a benefit for the public good, data providers will have to develop specific metrics of assessing a research contribution to societal aims, as well as monitor the extent to which such metrics are satisfactorily addressed by users. For example, it might be the case that a start-up, operating as a not-for-profit social enterprise, approaches data providers and requests access to data, promising to e.g. develop novel technology solutions that will improve the delivery of existing policies. Would such a disclosure be in the public interest? Would the answer be the same if the start-up considers the marketisation of their products in the long-run?

There is no silver bullet to resolve the tensions inherent in determining the ‘public interest’ in data access and governance, but there are a few central considerations for data providers when assessing whether a request serves the societal welfare. First, the identity of the requesting parties: are they affiliated with a research organisation? Are they accredited? Are they independent? Second, the types of data requested: is it necessary for the proposed project? Could a more or less granular approach be implemented? Does the request respect the principles of data minimization and security? Third, the intended purpose: is it consistent with data subjects’ reasonable expectations as to how the data providers would use their data? Have the

risks associated with the request been evaluated in a comprehensive manner? Fourth, the possibility of subsequent re-use: do the requesters seek to retain the requested data for future research or other re-use? Policy-makers would benefit from reflecting on these questions, in the interest of adopting a consistent position that will allow them to maximise the impact of administrative data for the public good.

5. Conclusion: Power Asymmetries and Ethical Scrutiny

To think that overcoming the ‘public’ / ‘private’ divide in data access and governance is to uncritically allow access to public datasets would be throwing the baby out with the bathwater. The proposed in this paper classification of public interest research provides clarity as to the critical factor, i.e. societal welfare and not the individual interests of a data provider, but does not exhaust the realm of necessary governance solutions if such welfare is to be realised.

The previous example of the power asymmetry between private companies and public bodies is by no means an outlier. As business models increasingly rely on the monetisation of data assets, commercial entities have moved beyond the use of ‘open’ government data (e.g. satellite data) and have sought and gained access to identifiable, personal information about such categories of individuals as users of national health services and justice systems (Magrath, 2019). With high-profile data mishandling cases like Cambridge Analytica being very recent, stakeholders in the UK have been proposing the requirement of explicit consent of individual citizens in any partnership where their data is being shared to a commercial enterprise (Ada Lovelace Institute, 2019).

Similar questions are likely to create even more dramatic tensions in developing countries, where the contribution of private, often multinational, enterprises will be much needed to realise data-driven public sector reform and high-quality research into major social problems. Beyond legal compliance, rigorous ethical scrutiny of data access requests is needed to ensure that public-private data partnerships indeed serve the social well-being, without creating excessive risks for data subjects. Developed countries should carefully consider their role in encouraging and facilitating the imposition of such scrutiny against the backdrop of increasing economic

pressures faced by developing countries, especially after the pandemic.

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